

Semantic features and new methods of non-standard English

Shodiyeva Gulrux Nazir kizi
FerSU, Linguistics, master

Sayfidinova Aziza Tolibovna
FerSU, Linguistics, master

Annotation: This article describes the semantic features of non-standard English, its styles and types. There are also some obscene words related to the American slang and their meanings. Our goal is to provide English learners with a brief overview of the semantic features of non-standard English, which are widely used in communication today.

Аннотация: В статье описаны семантические особенности нестандартного английского языка, его стили и типы. Есть также несколько нецензурных слов, относящихся к американскому сленгу и их значениям. Наша цель - предоставить изучающим английский язык краткий обзор семантических особенностей нестандартного английского языка, которые сегодня широко используются в общении.

Keywords: functional style, expression style, colloquialism, jargon, argon, vulgarism, slang.

Ключевые слова: функциональный стиль, экспрессивный стиль, разговорный язык, жаргон, аргон, вульгаризм, сленг.

Today, the rapid development of political, economic, cultural and scientific relations of independent Uzbekistan with foreign countries requires careful study and learning of foreign languages. Changes in the education system require a radical overhaul of the teaching of foreign languages, as well as all the subjects specified in the curricula of secondary schools, vocational colleges, academic lyceums, universities in the country. is doing. The resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated August 11, 2017 No. 610 "On measures to further improve the teaching of foreign languages in educational institutions" plays an important role in achieving this goal. The resolution consists of 6 paragraphs, each of which describes the aspects of teaching a foreign language, ie English. If we want to learn English perfectly, we must try not to ignore its linguistic features. We all know that every language has its own internal structure. English is no exception. Regardless of style or stylistic color, languages have neutral words that are used only for specific situations. Words of this form are more commonly found in dictionaries, and we call them words of non-literary or non-standard lexicon. In this article, we will talk about this, that is, non-standard English. Considering his methods before focusing on non-standard words will help to further enrich our understanding of this. According to him, there are two types of methods: functional and

expressive. Functional style is defined as a method of communication used between a certain group of people and used for a specific purpose. Examples include the craft style, the verbal style, the scientific style, and so on. The next style is this style of expression. Expression is a style in which words express their emotional feelings in a particular situation.

Such methods are interpreted by different linguists using different terms. As an example, according to the Russian linguist R. G. Pyotrovsky, styles are divided into high-level, lavish poetry-related and scientific language styles, i.e., literary storytelling, literary speaking styles, and other non-basic sub-styles. In one place we find a low-level style, that is, a non-standard style of speech and the words and phrases in it - colloquialism ("colloquial" - from the English phrase "phrases and expressions specific to the style of speech"), slang ("Slang" from English "slang, words of ordinary oral vocabulary"), general slang, special slang (slang and slang-special words) and vulgarism (rough words). Colloquialism stands between standard and non-standard vocabulary. However, some linguists call colloquialisms non-standard vocabulary. For example, E. Partridge in his book "The World of Words" provides the necessary information about the fact that colloquialism is "lower" than the standard lexicon, but higher than the slang. Based on this idea, we can think of colloquialisms as a type of non-standard lexicon as well as an introduction to standard lexicon. Jargon is a set of special words and phrases that are understood only by a narrow group of people, but not by other categories of people. Slang is a set of words and phrases that belong to a certain social group, ie a group of people of the same age and activity (the language of athletes, the language of a gang of criminals). style. However, linguists have not been able to come to a definite conclusion on this point, that is, whether slang and argon are special slang or some other part of non-standard lexicon. Another form of non-standard lexicon is vulgarisms. Vulgarisms are a collection of words with rough and sharp qualities. In standard English, vulgarism is recognized as a taboo. We know that the main part of non-standard English is the oral style used in oral speech, which is called slang. Below we prove a number of examples of American slang. A number of suffixes ("affixation") and prefixes ("prefix") are added to the word "prefix". suffixes ("suffix" - English "suffix that forms a new word by adding to the end of a word") and infixes ("infix" - English word o Additions that include a suffix that forms a new word by adding it to the suffix ') will help. Let's take a look at these types of attachments one by one. The most common of these non-standard word-formative suffixes is the earth suffix. For example, "greener" - a new person or an inexperienced employee ("green" - green, newly sprouted), "juiser" - alcoholic, ("juise" - juice, drink), "penciller" - journalist ("pencil" - pen) .Another addition is the suffix bu-ie, which means to belittle, flatter, or degrade people. For example, "drunkie" is a drunkard; ("Baddie" - evil, bad); "goodie" - good man, ("good" - good). The negative prefix is used in the non-American slang to denote a deficiency: "no-hoper" - an unlucky, useless person ("hope"); ("No-name" (insignificant person) ("name" -ism); ("No-noise" - an invisible person who did not come). The next unit that makes up the word is the "population" suffix. For example, "workaholic" - hardworking, dedicated to work ("work" - to work); ("New Yorkaholic" - loyal to New

York) "New York" - New York. There are also semi-suffix proof, -man, -land, -like, -hood, -head, etc., which also serve to make slang words.

In conclusion, all of the above information will help us to get acquainted with modern English and to communicate freely not only with the literary language, but also with those who speak it. This is because, as mentioned above, non-standard English is far from a literary language, but it is a widely used style of communication.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi bosh vaziri : A.Aripov Toshkent.sh.,2017-yil 11-avgust,610-son
- 2.Partridge.E "The World of Words" London, 1938
- 3.Piotrovskiy.R.G."Сосуществующие фонетические системы и стилистические корреляции в молдавском языке // Проблемы структурной лингвистики"1962